

A Survey on Machine Learning Methods in EEG-Based Authentication

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Abstract—Biometrics-based user authentication is a challenging problem in the present day with manifold applications in border control, building access, online banking, and others. In this study, our objective is to review the state of the art in user authentication through EEG with the objective of evaluating authentication performances. Previous surveys on the topic of EEG-based user authentication have been published by Jayarathne et al. [26] and Bidgoly et al. [14], however a review of the performance of specific machine learning algorithms have not been evaluated in this field. We review the existing state-of-the-art and assess the performance of the Machine Learning based methodologies, which has authenticated users through EEG. We have studied their utilization of components for the Machine Learning pipeline which includes data collection methodologies, feature extraction, and user classification techniques. We have identified that the best performing algorithms are k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest. The accuracies achieved with kNN and SVM are 99.14% (Correct Recognition Rate) by Wang et al. [60] and 99.0% by Nakamura et al. [44] respectively when users are in a resting state. On the other hand random forest achieves a accuracy of 99.9% by Rahman et al. [48] when EEG is fused with keystroke biometrics. Another well performing algorithm is Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) producing an accuracy of 98.24% when users are exposed to visual stimuli.

Keywords— Biometrics, electroencephalography, machine learning, performance, user identification

I. INTRODUCTION

Biometrics based user authentication is applied for manifold purposes like border security, law enforcement, banking, device security, building access, and others [39] [16] [4]. Several physiological and/or behavioral biometric modalities (iris, face, fingerprint, voice, signature, gait, keypress, touch-events, mouse dynamics, physiological signals) can be utilized for such human verification and identification purposes [16]. In a user identification based system, a user is distinguished from other users through valid identifying credentials. User identification is categorized in three types - knowledge-based, possession-based, and inherent-based [2]. In knowledge-based identification, a user is authenticated by proving their knowledge of a secret token or password, such as PINs or TANs (used in e-banking transactions) [31]. In possession-based identification, user identification is performed using a token in the user's possession, including photo-id cards, bank cards, RFID (Radio-frequency identification) tags [51]. Inherent-based identification is performed with a user's biometric data such as iris,

fingerprint, signature, gait, typing, and swiping biomedical signals [2]. Knowledge-based and possession-based identifications are disadvantageous as they can be easily compromised and are prone to spoof attacks [54], [23]. In contrast, an inherent-based system captures the user's unique physiological or behavioural metrics over time [30], and is therefore difficult to forge.

The brain activity of a user can be used as a modality for such an inherent-based user authentication system. Brain activity is monitored using electroencephalography (EEG), a classical tool which involves the placement of electrodes on the user's scalp for recording electrical activity generated by the brain [19]. EEG is categorized into five frequency bands depending on the activity and mental state of a subject. The EEG frequency bands are delta (0.5-4 Hz), theta (4-8 Hz), alpha (8-12 Hz), beta (12-30 Hz), and gamma bands (>30 Hz) [45]. EEG based authentication can be performed using a subset of the available frequency bands [27]. The relative activity of the sub-bands changes according to the task being performed by the individual [12], [50], [22], therefore isolating a specific sub-band may also provide relevant user identification data [28], [56].

It is standard to measure biometrics against seven characteristics. These characteristics are Universality, Uniqueness, Permanence, Collectability, Performance, Acceptability, and Circumvention (Often called Security) [42] [10]. The definition of each characteristic can be found in Table I.

Characteristic	Description
Universality	Biometric is available from every individual
Uniqueness	Biometric is different for every individual
Permanence	Biometric does not change over time
Collectability	Biometric is easily measurable
Performance	Biometric must be accurate and stable
Acceptability	Biometric is used by the public willingly
Security	Biometric must be difficult to spoof

TABLE I: The seven characteristics of biometric technologies.

As a user authentication modality, EEG features the seven biometric characteristics in the following ways:

Universality - EEG data can be obtained from any living individual.

Fig. 1: Pipeline of user authentication technique through EEG

Uniqueness - EEG can be utilized as biometric modality that distinguishes one user from other.

Permanence - EEG data is available from any living individual even if the other sources of physiological biometric data is compromised due to injury.

Collectability - In present day there are many advanced EEG capturing devices with fewer electrodes and which makes the installation and data-capture processes easier [26].

Performance - There are many studies [48], [7], [26] where user authentication through EEG show high performance.

Acceptability - EEG data can be easily logged from the electrodes to preexisting software interfaces without requiring user intervention [16]. In the cases of typing-based and touch-based recognition, a user needs to interact with an interface. Although users need to put on a wearable device (Acticap, electrodes [18], headsets, wrist devices [15], and EEG-based glasses [35]).

Security - EEG-based authentication cannot be easily forged, and hence has anti-spoofing characteristics, unlike fingerprints, face, handwriting identification.

Motivated by the biometric characteristics of EEG, our evaluation aims to provide more information on the user authentication research platforms. For this, we thoroughly study the most recent (2014 onward) peer-reviewed scientific publications. The rest of the work on performance evaluation of an EEG based system is arranged as follows: Section II presents a summary of the review which directs to a table documenting the comparisons of the surveyed literature. Section III discusses the methods of EEG data collection methodologies across the surveyed studies. Section IV summarizes the authentication mechanisms through the selection of different modules across the state-of-the-art. Section V

groups the studies using the classification model used and forms a correlation of such selected models with the authentication performance. Section VI discusses the overall nature of our survey and the key takeaways. Finally, Section VII concludes our study.

II. REVIEW SUMMARY

We have reviewed a few notable EEG-based authentication studies, of which [35], [40], [48], [49], and [58] used additional biometric modalities in addition to EEG for user identification. Other works classify users through EEG as the only modality. The reviewed studies are tabulated in Table II. The purpose of this survey is to focus on the notable selected studies and analyze each module of their respective EEG-based authentication pipeline, which makes this study more in-depth. Our goal is to observe the performance of the authentication through the lens of the selected state-of-the-art and how the selection of their modules in the EEG-pipeline benefited their authentication performance.

III. DATA ACQUISITION

User authentication is performed by comparing data obtained from an individual claiming to be a user to stored data known to belong to said user. If the individual's data is found to match the stored data, the individual is authenticated as the user. In order to ensure high authentication accuracy, an established user task and data collection protocol should be implemented. By providing high quality initial data collection, the rate of false negatives and false positives in user authentication systems can be reduced. Additionally, providing data collection protocols that remain invariable across time should improve the user authentication rate.

A. Data Collection Variables

There are multiple variables that must be considered when assessing an EEG data acquisition protocol. The following list details variables that can impact the applicability of acquired EEG data, as well as describing the practice observed in the reviewed state-of-the-art for each of these criteria:

Fig. 2: EMOTIV Headset Electrode Positioning

Electrode Choice- EEG data may be obtained using various numbers of electrodes. The studies in this review use headsets with a range of 2 [28] to 128 [60] electrodes. In the related studies, the use of non-invasive methods of EEG data collection is performed utilizing commercially available EEG headsets such as EMOTIV [27], [48], [13], and different head caps (Easy cap/Acti-cap) [40], [58], [49], and [21]. Figure 2 shows placement of EMOTIV headset on a user. Figure 3 shows an acti-cap which is also used to collect EEG. Electrode placements on the scalp may follow the standard international 10-20 electrode placement method. It is an internationally recognized method to apply the location of scalp electrodes (irrespective of the number) for an EEG exam, sleep study, or voluntary lab research. Studies like [57], [20], [59], and [58] have followed the 10-20 electrode placement technique. The "10" and "20" refer to the fact that the actual distances between adjacent electrodes are either 10% or 20% of the total front-back or right-left distance of the skull. The study by Kosmyna et al. [35] have used wearable EEG recording glasses which also records Electrooculogram (EOG) data. Nakamura et al. [44] have used an in-ear plugin EEG sensor where each earplug has 2 electrodes. The material of the plugs is a viscoelastic foam that fits into the user's ears. The study by Zhang et al. [64] have used electrodes placed on user's forehead. Figure 4 shows the placement of electrodes using the 10-20 system.

Number of Participants The number of participants recruited for data collection in the reviewed studies ranges from 4 [60] to 119 [57]. Data collection durations vary amongst studies from one session to several days. Arnau-Gonzalez et al. [9] have used three public datasets in their study where the datasets have 32, 27, and 15 users.

Sampling Rate - The sampling rate of an electrode channel is determined by the number of EEG samples collected per second. The range of sampling rates in the

Fig. 3: EEG data collection using acti-cap [40]

Fig. 4: The electrode positions in the 10-10 system, labeled according to each electrode's position relative to the lobes of the brain [1]

reviewed studies is from 128 Hz [27], [13] to 2400 Hz [61].

B. User Behavior

Brain activity can be recorded for any number of user tasks. However, most data for EEG user authentication consists of simple tasks with minimized external influences due to the increased simplicity of task replication. The task performed by the user is typically of short duration to improve system user-friendliness and is often performed with minimal need for secondary devices where possible. Because the brain is active at all times, brain data can be collected when the subject is awake, relaxed, asleep, or during physical activities. A full listing of the user tasks in the reviewed state-of-the-art can be seen in Table II. The following list describes a taxonomy for common user tasks performed in data acquisition:

Resting - The most common type of user task seen in the state-of-the-art is resting, wherein a user is typically seated and not exposed to any source of external stimuli. Resting data is useful for monitoring a user's brain activity baseline to use in conjunction with other user tasks such that an action can be distinguished from a non-action. Resting data may be used by itself as input for a user authentication system. During a resting task, the user may be asked to rest with their eyes closed (REC),

Study	Modality	#User	Behavior	EEG device	Duration	SR (Hz)	Algorithm	Best performance
Abdulrahman et al. [3]	EEG	-		BCI	-	-	SVM, kNN	90.8%, ACC
Albasri et al. [7]	EEG	109	EO, EC, relax	-	-	160	GA, SVM	97.9%, ACC
Arnau-González et al. [9]	EEG	50	EO, EC	-	3 session	256	MD, ED, CD	90.8%, IR
Bashar et al. [13]	EEG	9	relax, EO, stimuli	EMOTIV headset	6 weeks	128	SVM	94.44%, TPR
Chin et al. [17]	EEG	20	task(EC)	Truscan	-	1024	kNN, LDA	98.03%, ACC
Di et al. [20]	EEG	10	EO, EC, rest	-	2 weeks	1000	SVM, PCC	80-100%, ACC
Gui et al. [21]	EEG	30	read	Easy Cap	2 session	500	ED, DTW	72.5%, ACC
Jayarathne et al. [27]	EEG	12	relax(EC), stimuli(EO), recall(EC)	-	-	128	LDA, SVM, kNN	99%, ACC
Jijomon and Vinod. [28]	EEG	20	sit(EC), stimuli	Brain-Prod.cap	4 trials	500	NN	99.97%, ACC
Koike-Akino et al. [33]	EEG	25	count	EMOTIV EPOC	2 session	128	LDA, NB, DT, kNN, SVM, LR	96.7%, ACC
Kosmyna et al. [35]	EEG, EOG	-	-	AttentivU glasses	-	1000	-	-
Luciw et al. [40]	EEG, EMG	12	grasp, lift	Cap	-	500	-	-
Maiorana et al. [41]	EEG	50	EO, EC	Galileo	3 session	256	MD, ED, CD	90.8%, IR
Nakamura et al. [44]	EEG	15	rest(EC)	In-Ear plug	3 trials	1200	SVM, LDA, CD	99%, ACC
Rahman et al. [48]	EEG, Key-press	10	typing password	EMOTIV headset	10 session	-	kNN, LDA, SVM, RF	99.9%, ACC
Ruiz-Blondet et al. [49]	EEG, EOG,	56	stimuli	Easy Cap	1 Hour	500	CC	68-100%, ACC
Thomas and Vinod [56]	EEG	109	EO, EC	-	-	160	CC	0.01%, EER
Valizadeh et al. [57]	EEG	144	rest(EC)	Brain Prod.	2 session	1000	LDA, kNN, SVM, NN, RF	100%, AUC
Wang et al. [58]	EEG Face	-	stimuli	Cap	120 trials	2048	CC	96.67%, ACC
Wang et al. [59]	EEG	109, 59	motor move, attention(EO, EC)	BCI, Dry electrodes	20 Hours	160	MahD	69.98, CRR%
Wang et al. [60]	EEG	4	rest(EC)	BrainProd.	2 session	250	kNN	99.14%, CRR
Wu et al. [61]	EEG	45	stimuli	-	2 session	2400	DCA	91.31%, ACC
Yang et al. [62]	EEG	109, 122	rest(EO, EC), stimuli	BCI2000, headset	60 seconds	160, 256	LDA	98.24%, ACC
Zhang et al. [64]	EEG	46	relax(EO, EC)	MindWave	7 minutes	512	kNN, LDA, SVM	80-95%, ACC

TABLE II: Comparative Literature Review. Abbreviations used- ACC: Accuracy; AUC:Area Under the Curve; BCI: Brain-Computer Interface; CC: Cross-Correlation; CD: Cosine Distance; CRR: Correct Recognition Rate; DCA: Discriminant Component Analysis; DT: Decision Trees; DTW: Dynamic Time Warping; EC: Eyes Closed; ED: Euclidean Distance; EER: Equal Error Rate; EO: Eyes Opened; GA: Genetic Algorithm; IO: Identification Rate; kNN: k-Nearest Neighbor; LDA: Linear Discriminant Analysis; LR: Logistic Regression; MD: Manhattan Distance; NN:Neural Network; PCC: Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient; RF: Random Forest; SVM: Support Vector Machine; TPR: True Positive Rate

or with their eyes open (REO). In the reviewed state-of-the-art, both REC [17], [56], [41], [64], [62], [27], [60], [7], [13], [57], [20], [59], [44], and REO, [27], [7], [20], [56], [59], [13], [64], [62], [41], [48], are used.

Stimulus - A user may be exposed to a sensory stimulus to illicit a response that may be recorded using EEG. When a stimulus is exposed to the user, a synchronized spike of brain activity occurs approximately 300 ms after exposure. This spike is known as the P300. The stimulus to which a user is exposed can be reliant on any of the human senses (sight, smell, hearing, touch, taste), however visual and auditory stimuli are most often used due to the ease with which these can be reliably replicated in most environments. Using a stimuli provides a strong response in a localized region of the brain that is easily detectable by EEG, although it is also disadvantageous due to the reliance on external devices to produce the stimuli. In the reviewed state-of-the-art, both visual stimuli [27], [61], [58], [9], [62], [49] and auditory stimuli [58], [28], [21], user tasks are utilized in user authentication.

Mental Tasks - Active tasks that require the user to to utilize a cognitive workload with or without the need for physical movement qualify as mental tasks. Examples of mental tasks include solving math problems, counting and spelling (in the individuals mind), pattern recall, and descriptive tasks. Mental tasks may be complex and often utilize extensive connective networks for the completion of the given task. However due to learning curves, it is possible for the user's response to mental tasks to improve over time, thus altering the EEG response detected. This may prove disadvantageous to long-term stability of user authentication accuracy. The mental tasks observed in the reviewed state-of-the-art are counting tasks [33], attention tasks [59], descriptive tasks [59], password typing tasks [48], and reading tasks [21], [49].

Motor Imagery & Movement - When a user must perform a physical movement, or when a user imagines performing a physical movement without actually physically moving. The act of physically moving is termed movement (MOT), while the act of imaging physical movement is called motor imagery (MI). Both MOT and MI tasks activate the same synchronized neural pathways, making MI a highly studied user task for application in prosthesis. Due to the high level of synchronization, MOT and MI data can be easily detected using EEG. In the reviewed state-of-the-art, both MOV [17], [59], [40], and MI [17], [59], are observed.

We have discussed three traits [13] of collecting EEG data for identification- i) while relaxation when eyes closed [17], [56], [41], [64], [62], [27], [60], [7], [13], [57], [20], [59]; ii) while exposed to stimuli [62], [49], [58], [27], [60], [7], [13], [20], [59]; and iii) while performing mental tasks [17], [33], [21], [27], [48], [40], [59]. Identification using EEG may utilize one or more of these traits. All reviewed studies use EEG as the identifying modality. Additional modalities such as keypress data [48], electromyographic (EMG) data [40], electrooculogram (EOG) data [33], [49], and face [58] are also collected along with EEG data. Jijomon and

Vinod [28] had their participants in an eyes-closed resting state and exposed participants to 3-second auditory clips of names. The names consisted of both unfamiliar names, and 10 familiar names such that the auditory evoked potentials in response to both cases could be observed. Arnau-Gonzalez et al. [9] have used datasets that exposed users to video stimuli, to elicit emotions. Wu et al. [61] have presented users with a Rapid Serial Visual Presentation (RSVP) of multiple images of the same resolution. Users in this study have viewed images of their own and of different people where the presentation of each image is of 300 ms duration. This process will result in high Event-Related Potentials (ERP). Users are asked to focus on their own face images and count the number of occurrences of the self-face images in their minds.

IV. COMPONENTS OF AUTHENTICATION PIPELINE PIPELINE

Machine learning (ML) is performed by applying an algorithm or mathematical model to a dataset such that new data can be classified into labeled classes. In this study, we reviewed state-of-art ML methodologies used for EEG-based user authentication. We discuss below the ML techniques used in the reviewed works in various stages of classification. Figure 1 shows a typical Machine Learning pipeline for user authentication through EEG data. In this section, we discuss various usages of key components of such pipeline using our surveyed studies.

A. Data Preprocessing

There are several methods of processing EEG data. Jayarathne et al. [27] perform data augmentation using methods such as jittering and random sampling as the 12 volunteers only provide a small amount of data samples over short sessions. Wang et al. [60] utilize Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to group the best set of electrodes suitable for identification. The EEG and keypress-based identification by Rahman et al. [48] utilize a sequence of data processing like filtering, segmentation (windowing), and resampling. Whereas the study by Luciw et al. [40] only involves filtering EEG through a bandpass filter. Albasri et al. [7] and Valizadeh et al. [57] use Independent Component Analysis (ICA) to remove the heart and eye artifact components infused with the EEG and then segment the data into 60-second time windows. Di et al. [20] passed the signal through a 1 - 40 Hz band-pass filter, after which the 450-second observation was segmented into 450 1-second windows. A similar band-pass filtering approach was performed by Jijomon and Vinod [28]. Later they segment the data into 200 millisecond sliding widows. The study by Kosmyna et al. [35] in their collection of both EEG and EOG data, performs processing by utilizing a low-pass filter of 50 Hz and a high-pass filter of 0.5 Hz. There are a few studies where the data is downsampled from the original sampling rate. Studies like [20] and [9] have downsampled their own dataset and public datasets respectively which originally have a very high sampling rate. In the study by Wang et al. [58], they downsampled the data from 2048 Hz to 128 Hz with anti-aliasing filter.

Study	Filters for data processing
Abdulrahman et al. [3]	Band-pass filter to remove noise.
Albasri et al. [7]	Band-pass filter for extracting EEG sub-bands.
Arnau-González et al. [9]	High-pass filtered with a 2 Hz cut-off frequency for one of the public datasets.
Bashar et al. [13]	Band-pass FIR filter to remove body motion effects and noise.
Chin et al. [17]	Butterworth filter to retrieve EEG sub-bands.
Di et al. [20]	Band-pass filter of 1–40 Hz.
Gui et al. [21]	Not specified.
Jayarathne et al. [27]	Moving average filter to remove high frequencies and random noise.
Jijomon et al. [28]	10th order Butterworth band-pass filter to retrieve EEG sub-bands.
Koike-Akino et al. [33]	Blind source separation canonical correlation analysis (BSS-CCA) to remove ocular artifacts.
Kosmyna et al. [35]	1st order low- and high-pass filters with cut-off frequencies of 50Hz and 0.5Hz respectively.
Luciw et al. [40]	Band-pass filter with cut-off frequency range of 0.016–1000 Hz.
Maiorana et al. [41]	Band-pass filter to retrieve the EEG sub-bands.
Nakamura et al. [44]	4th order Butterworth filter with pass-band of 0.5-30Hz.
Rahman et al. [48]	Band-pass infinite impulse response (IIR) filter with a cut-off frequency of 0.5 Hz and 63 Hz used to remove noise.
Ruiz-Blondet et al. [49]	Band-pass filter to retrieve 1-55Hz.
Thomas et al. [56]	Band-pass filter to retrieve 0.5-50Hz.
Valizadeh et al. [57]	High-pass filter with a cut-off frequency of 0.1Hz.
Wang et al. [58]	Band-pass filter to retrieve 0.1-42Hz.
Wang et al. [59]	Band-pass filter to retrieve 0.5-42Hz.
Wang et al. [60]	Independent Component Analysis to remove eye movement, noise, and muscle artifacts.
Wu et al. [61]	Low-pass Chebyshev digital filter with a pass-band of 40Hz and a stop-band of 49Hz.
Yang et al. [62]	Not specified.
Zhang et al. [64]	Chebyshev filter and zero-phase filtering applied for 0–60 Hz low-pass filtering.

TABLE III: Filters used in the reviewed studies during data processing stage.

After which the signal is band-pass filtered between 0.1 Hz to 42 Hz to retain only relevant frequencies. Yang et al. [62] performs Wavelet Packet Decomposition after segmenting the raw data. Table III shows the types of filters utilised by the reviewed studies as part of the data processing stage.

B. Feature Extraction

EEG signals are made up of spontaneous voltage fluctuations resulting from mental and physical user activities. To characterize EEG data in a way that involves less processing power, a series of features may be extracted from measurements or structural components from a segment of the signal [6]. Features may be extracted from the time-domain, or the frequency-domain of a transformed signal. In the time-domain, methods such as Principle Component Analysis (PCA), AutoRegressive modelling (AR), and Independent-Component Analysis (ICA) are frequently used for feature extraction [38]. Multiple methods are available to convert EEG recordings from time-domain to frequency-domain. Of these, the most popular methods are Fast-Fourier Transforms (FFT), Wavelet Transforms (WT), and Wavelet Packet Decomposition (WPD) [38], [6]. The specific features to be extracted for a given system varies according to the tasks being performed by the user. The most commonly used features for user authentication in the reviewed state-of-the-art are described below. Additionally, we have tabulated the features per state-of-the-art in Table IV.

Statistical Features- Statistical features are simple and widely used in EEG signal analysis. These features describe the statistical information of signal segments using measurements from time-domain and frequency-domain EEG data [55]. A statistical feature is determined by extracting information from each sample across a specified time-segment to produce a population on which statistical analysis can be performed [53]. Because statistical features are able to describe trends across larger sets of data, they can be useful in reducing the processing power required to classify a complete dataset. The statistical features observed in the surveyed state-of-the-art are mean and standard deviation [7], [17], [13], [64], [48], variance [17], [13], median [48], [17], mode, maximum and minimum [17], 1st and 2nd difference [64], entropy [13], [3], [48], percentiles, skewness, kurtosis [48], K-order origin distance, and K-order center distance [64]. Statistical features are calculated from the power-spectrum density data in Chin et al. [17], while Bashar et al. [13] and Wang et al. [60] extract these features from each individual frequency band of the signal.

Global Features- Global features use the entirety of the available data within a determined segment of an EEG recording to find correlations between multiple signal values across both space and time [29]. The spatial and temporal connectivity between voltage potentials may be evaluated using global features to identify patterns across the network of available electrodes, potentially revealing links between neuronal activity [63]. Despite the advantages provided by correlating data, global features

are often only capable of evaluating summaries of the relationship trends, in contrast to individually correlating local features to provide detailed classifications [36] [43]. If the global features are extracted to study the neuronal response to a sensory, motor, or cognitive event, the features are collectively known as an Event-Related Potential (ERPs) [24]. The global features in use may be statistical, frequency, or any other type of features that are correlated [5]. In the reviewed state-of-the-art, Wang et al. [59] extract transitivity, modularity, network characteristic path length, global efficiency, and network radius global features to record ERPs. Multiple papers [49], [28], [33], [58] use global invoked reaction EEG data to study ERPs. Wu et al. [61] extract spatial and temporal features, but do not record a specific event-related response to generate an ERP. A new global feature called Inter-Hemispherical Amplitude Ratio (IHAR) is used by Jayarathne et al. [27].

Spectral Features- The transformation of EEG data from the time-domain to the frequency-domain exposes a new range of signal characteristics from which spectral features can be extracted [47]. One such spectral feature is the power spectral density of a signal. The PSD is obtained by squaring the magnitude of the frequency components making up a signal [32]. Alternatively, the PSD can be calculated using the Welch method which averages the magnitude of frequency components using a sliding window, or the Burg method can be used in which an AR model prediction model is used to generate the PSD estimate [46]. Another feature that can be extracted from the frequency-domain is spectral coherence (COH), in which the constancy of phase differences between two signals is measured in a bivariate manner [37]. In the reviewed state-of-the-art PSD is used as a feature by multiple papers [20], [41], [17], [9], [44]. The absolute PSD is used by Thomas et al. [56] by summing the power of each frequency band. COH is utilized by Maiorana et al. [41]. Additional spectral features such as maximum frequency, spectral entropy, and average power are extracted by Rahman et al. [48]. Average spectral power is used as a feature in [60], [48]

Frequency Bands- The five sub-bands of EEG data can be accessed by segmenting the data into the accepted frequency ranges for each band by WT decomposition or by band-pass filtering signals [34]. Sub-bands may be isolated such that they can be used to generate a set of features for each band [8], or the global data contained within each band may be used to model connectivity [25]. When a user activity is known to be associated with a specific mental-state, only a specific subset of frequency bands may be used to reduce the size of the dataset that must be processed [11], [65]. In the reviewed state-of-the-art, both WT [60], [13], [48] and band-pass filtering [7], [41], [28] have been used to extract the frequency sub-bands from the complete EEG dataset. In these studies, the individual bands were used to generate statistical features [60], [13], [7] spectral features [41], [7], and ERPs [28]. Both Rahman et al. and Zhang et al. separate their EEG data into custom sub-bands, of which

18 and 28 sub-bands where computed respectively.

Other Features- In Rahman et al. [48], a keyboard is used to record keystroke data that is used alongside the EEG recording. In this study, the key-hold time, key-down to key-down time, key-up to key-up time, and key-up to key-down time for keypresses are used as features that correspond to the recorded EEG data. Another feature used in the state-of-the-art is the zero-crossing rate (ZCR), which measures the rate at which data changes from positive to negative or vice-versa [52]. ZCR is extracted as a feature by Zhang et al [64]. An AR model is used to generate autocorrelation features in Maiorana et al. [41] and AR coefficients in Nakamura et al. [44].

C. Data Splitting

Data splitting is performed to train and test the classifier. These two sets cannot overlap. An optional validation set can be used [48], [28] for tuning classification parameters. Rahman et. al [48] have an 80:20 split for the training:testing set where 20% of the training set is used for validation. The study by Bashar et al. [13] has training and testing sets where 5001 samples per channel are divided into five segments, three of which are used for training, and the remaining are used for testing. Data from 15 trials are augmented and split into training and testing in the study by Jayarathne et al. [27]. Study by Wang et. al [60] and Abdulrahman et al. [3] have a 50:50 split between training and testing data. They performed both intra-session (train/test data from the same session) and inter-session (train/test data from different sessions) experiments. Di et al. [20] have a 50:50 split between training and testing datasets. Jijimon et al. [28], Nakamura et al. [44], and Arnau-Gonzalez et al. [9] have split the data into training, validation, and testing. Wang et al. [59] and Wu et al. [61] have split their data into training and testing with 5-fold and 10-fold cross-validations respectively. The studies by Wang et al. [58] and Ruiz-Blondet [49] do not require training as they are using cross-correlation to classify users. Yang et al. [62] have used the data from eyes open and eyes closed sessions for training and testing interchangeably. Thomas et al. [56] splits the one minute data per user into 8 non-overlapping 7.5 seconds segments. Out of which, 7 segments are used for training, and the remaining 1 is used for testing.

V. CLASSIFICATION -

An algorithm may follow supervised learning, in which case the algorithm learns the data labels along with the observations and predicts the labels of the test samples. In contrast, an unsupervised learning algorithm learns unlabeled observations and transforms them into another vector. Algorithms may also be parametric or non-parametric. In parametric algorithms, the information about the distribution of the population is known or is assumed and is based on a fixed set of parameters. In non-parametric algorithms, the information about the distribution of a population is unknown, and the param-

eters are not fixed, which makes it necessary to test the hypothesis for the population.

The state-of-the-arts has utilized different Machine Learning based classifiers and performed classification for identifying individuals based on EEG data. The performance of the classification were measured through several metrics like accuracy, Equal Error Rate (EER), Area Under the Curve (AUC) of a Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, True Positive Rate (TPR), False Positive Rate (FPR), F1 value (based on precision and recall), and others. We have grouped the machine learning algorithms used by the state-of-the-art and listed the best performance achieved.

A. *K-Nearest Neighbor (kNN)*

The k-nearest neighbor algorithm (kNN) is a supervised, non-parametric classification model. Contrary to other learning algorithms that allow discarding the training data after the model is built, kNN keeps all training examples in memory. Once a previously unseen example x comes in, the kNN algorithm finds k training examples closest to x and returns the majority label, in case of classification, or the average label, in case of regression. The closeness of the two examples is given by a distance function. Euclidean distance is frequently used in practice. Another popular choice of the distance function is the negative cosine similarity. In Jayarathne et al. [27], multiple classification algorithms are compared with the kNN clustering technique achieving the best result of 99% of AUC. Wang et al. [60] also utilize kNN and achieves an accuracy of 92%. Valizadeh et al. [57] use a weighted variant of kNN, which achieved an accuracy of 100% over multiple trials using different connectivity measures. Chin et al. [17] utilize kNN and achieve an accuracy of 98.03%.

B. *Support Vector Machine (SVM)*

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a supervised machine learning algorithm. This algorithm operates by segregating data through the use of a hyperplane and creating boundaries. New data is classified by its placement within the created boundaries. Albasri et al. [7] utilizes a genetic algorithm to choose a group of electrodes and perform several classification-based experiments using SVM (Support Vector Machine) as the classifier, although the feature dimension is as low as three. In this study, the best EER of 0.03% is achieved when 11 electrodes are grouped. Rahman et al. [48] achieve an accuracy of 96.5% when both keypress and EEG are fused, using QSVM. Using SVM as the classifier, Bashar et al. [13] achieve a TPR of 94.44% at 5.56% FPR. Valizadeh et al. [57] achieve an accuracy of 100% using SVM over multiple trials using different connectivity measures. The accuracy varies between 80-100% in the time-robustness analysis by Di et al. [20] by utilizing SVM as the classifier. Nakamura et al. [44] utilized the earplug EEG sensor and achieved 99% of accuracy utilizing SVM as the classifier. Abdulrahman et al. [3] has achieved their best performance of 90.8% utilizing SVM as one of the classifiers. In Zhang et al. [64], among

kNN, LDA, and SVM, an accuracies ranging between 80-95% are achieved across several experiments when SVM is used.

C. *Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)*

Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) is a parametric supervised model that is used as a dimensionality reduction tool. This algorithm is used for both feature selection and classification. Valizadeh et al. [57] used LDA, in addition to other classifiers, over multiple trials using different connectivity measures and achieved an accuracy of 100%. Nakamura et al. [44] utilizes LDA in addition to SVM and achieves an accuracy of 95.7% by logging data through the ear-plug EEG sensor. In addition to utilizing algorithms like kNN, SVM, Jayarathne et al. [27] have also classified individuals using LDA where they achieved an AUC of 98.1%. The work by Yang et al. [62] achieves an accuracy of 98.24% with LDA as the classifier.

D. *Random Forest (RF)*

Random forest is a widely used learning algorithm. It uses multiple samples of the original dataset, which reduces the variance of the final model. Low variance implies low overfitting. Overfitting occurs when the model tries to reflect small variations in the dataset. Depending on how the training set is sampled, it could contain artifacts like noise, outliers, and over or underrepresented examples. By creating multiple random samples with the replacement of the training set, one may reduce the effect of these artifacts. This methodology is known as bagging. Studies like Valizadeh et al. [57] and Rahman et al. [48] have achieved accuracies as high as 99.9% in certain experimental instances.

E. *Other Algorithms*

There are many well-known distance algorithms like Manhattan, scaled-Manhattan, Euclidean, and Cosine Distance. Mahalanobis distance is one widely used distance metrics algorithms, which is a measure of the distance between a point P and a distribution D . It is a multi-dimensional generalization of the idea of measuring how many standard deviations away P is from the mean of D . This distance is zero for P at the mean of D and grows as P moves away from the mean along each principal component axis. If each of these axes is re-scaled to have unit variance, then the Mahalanobis distance corresponds to standard Euclidean distance in the transformed space. Among the reviewed studies, 4 different distance algorithms are used. Wang et al. [59] uses Mahalanobis distance metrics to predict subject identity. Maiorana et al. [41] and Gui et al. [21] have used Euclidian Distance as their distance metrics algorithm. The Euclidean distance is the straight line distance between two points. In a plane p_1 at (x_1, y_1) and p_2 at (x_2, y_2) the Euclidean distance is measured as $\sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2}$. On the other hand, Cosine Distance is utilized by both Nakamura et al. [44] and Maiorana et al. [41]. The cosine distance between two points x and y is defined as $(x.x)/(\sqrt{(x.x)}\sqrt{(y.y)})$

Study	Features extracted on the EEG data
Abdulrahman et al. [3]	Wavelet packet decomposition on 13 EEG channels; applying sample entropy and Shannon's entropy to extract features.
Albasri et al. [7]	64-channel data segmented into 60 seconds epochs. Statistical features (mean, standard deviation, and power) are extracted from each epoch.
Arnau-González et al. [9]	32 channels of EEG data taken from each public dataset; Power spectral density applied to each of the 32 channels and the difference between the spectral power of all the symmetrical pairs of electrodes on the right and left hemisphere (within the same bands) are computed as features. Feature dimension is therefore, 32 channels * 5 bands + 14 pairs * 5 bands = 230.
Bashar et al. [13]	Three wavelet decomposition methods are used for feature extraction; from each wavelet, mean, standard deviation, and entropy are extracted.
Chin et al. [17]	Welch's method and Burg's method to compute power spectral density as feature extraction; computing statistical features (Mean, median, mode, variance, standard deviation, minimum and maximum) from output of feature extraction.
Di et al. [20]	450 seconds data segmented into 450 windows of 1 second each. Power spectral density using Welch's method, amplitude spectrum, channel coherence and channel phase lag features are extracted.
Gui et al. [21]	No separate features. The processed 4-channel data are treated as features.
Jayarathne et al. [27]	The data is windowed from which, inter-hemispheric amplitude ratio (novel feature), laterality coefficient, waveform length, slope sign change, and auto-regressive coefficients were extracted as features.
Jijomon and Vinod [28]	Data was segmented into 2 second epochs. Windowed data is input to deep neural networks where feature extraction is done per window.
Koike-Akino et al. [33]	14-channel data windowed to 800 ms. The feature dimension is 14*103 = 1442 which undergoes dimensional reduction. No mention of the 103 features per channel.
Kosmyna et al. [35]	Novel EOG and EEG wearable sensors presented. No experiments performed.
Luciw et al. [40]	WAY_EEG_GAL data is presented. No experiments performed.
Maiorana et al. [41]	19-channel data (collected over sessions S1, S2, and S3) is segmented to 5 seconds window. Independent features extracted pr window are autocorrelation, power spectrum density, and spectral coherence. Data from different combination of sessions extracted with each feature is fused to perform feature level fusion experiments.
Nakamura et al. [44]	Data is segmented to several epochs (10, 20, 30, 60, 90 s). Power spectral density (PSD) and coefficients of an autoregressive (AR) model are extracted as features.
Rahman et al. [48]	5-channel EEG data is resampled to 1024 samples per segments from each of which mean, median, standard deviation, mean absolute deviation, 25th percentile, 75th percentile, inter quartile range, skewness, kurtosis, Hjorth activity, Hjorth mobility, Hjorth complexity, Shannon's entropy, spectral entropy, second max frequency, average band power, average of 18 frequency band wavelets features are computed. Feature importance is computed in later stage to choose the important features from the high dimensional feature set.
Ruiz-Blondet et al. [49]	No feature extraction is performed.
Thomas and Vinod [56]	19-channel data windowed at 1 second. Power spectral density (Welch's method) is extracted as feature from each channel and each EEG bands ($\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \theta$).
Valizadeh et al. [57]	32-channel data segmented into 2 seconds window. From each segment coherence correlation, phase correlation, instantaneous coherence, lagged coherence, total coherence, instantaneous phase connectivity, lagged phase connectivity, total phase connectivity, coherence mutual information, phase mutual information, coherence Granger causality and phase Granger causality are extracted as features.
Wang et al. [58]	Raw 19-channel EEG data is used as features.
Wang et al. [59]	64-channel data (database I) and 46-channel data (database II) are segmented into 1 second window. From each window transitivity, modularity, network characteristic path length, global efficiency, network radius and diameter features are extracted
Wang et al. [60]	128-channel EEG data is decomposed using continuous wavelet transform. A coefficient matrix of dimension F(frequency bins)*C(channels)*T(150,000 samples) is constructed. From the coefficient matrix, a 2 second segments are created from which average spectral power is computed as feature.
Wu et al. [61]	Data epoched at a range between 200-1000 ms from which spatial and temporal features are extracted.
Yang et al. [62]	Wavelet Packet Decomposition is performed. DCT (Discrete Cosine Transform) coefficient is extracted from each wavelet band as feature.
Zhang et al. [64]	Data segmented to 2 seconds window. From each window time domain features (zero crossing rate, mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variance, 1st difference, 2nd difference, K-order origin distance, K-order center distance) and frequency domain features ($\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \theta$ bands total frequency of 3-58 Hz is divided into 2 Hz segments from which differential entropy is calculated) are extracted.

TABLE IV: Features extracted from the EEG data by the reviewed studies.

Amongst the studies we have reviewed, Manhattan Distance is used only by Maiorana et al. [41]. Manhattan distance is the distance between two points measured along axes at right angles. In a plane with p_1 at (x_1, y_1) and p_2 at (x_2, y_2) the Manhattan distance is measured as $|x_1 - x_2| + |y_1 - y_2|$. Di et al. [20] have used Pearson's correlation coefficient for intra-user (correlation within

the same user) linear correlation. Studies like [57], [28], and [9] have utilized different deep learning algorithms for user identification which are not the scope of this study. In the future we may consider adding other state-of-the-art which perform EEG-based user authentication using deep learning models. At that instance, we need to focus on the network structure and the performance.

VI. DISCUSSION

The review found high user identification performances which are achieved by applying different Machine Learning algorithms on EEG data. However, when assessing the performances of the reviewed algorithms for user identification, the variance in the conditions under which the EEG data is collected and processed must be considered.

One such condition is the number of participants in each study. The number of participants in the reviewed studies ranges widely, with the lowest number of participants being 4 from Want et al. [60] and the largest number of participants being 144, of which 119 are used, from Valizadeh et al. [57]. Studies have shown that unique topographical maps can be obtained from a user's EEG data that are visually distinct from that of other users [27]. Other factors that may affect the identification performance is the number of electrodes used for recording, the behavior performed by users while the EEG data is collected, and the use of other modalities in identification (if any), and the choice of classification algorithms.

Having a large number of electrodes increases the number of locations from which EEG data can be recorded, and thus may produce discriminating factors to distinguish one user from another. The number of electrodes used in the reviewed studies range from 2 [28] to 128 [60].

However, having a large amount of data from several channels may cause latency due to increased processing time. To bypass this, one can use machine learning algorithms to reduce the channels through feature extraction and dimensionality reduction as is seen in Albasri et al. [7]. Additionally, one may choose a specific subset of electrodes for classification [28] which produce the best result.

VII. CONCLUSION

Several behaviors or activities have been performed by volunteers while the EEG data is logged. The most common activities include eyes open, eyes closed, resting/relaxing state, exposure to various stimuli (visual/auditory), and performance of imaginary and non-imaginary tasks. For example, the study by Chin et al. [17] uses imaginary and non-imaginary tasks for user identification, while auditory and visual stimulation is used by Jijomon et al. [28] and Wu et al. [61] respectively. Resting state activity with eyes-open and eyes-closed are used by a large number of the reviewed studies, such as Nakamura et al. [44], Zhang et al. [64], and Wang et al. [60].

Within all the algorithms reviewed, the best performances are as follows: 100% accuracy for kNN, SVM, and LDA from Valizadeh et al. [57]. A 99.9% accuracy has been achieved for Random Forest by both Rahman et al [48] and Valizadeh et al. [57].

Within the studies that utilize both eyes-open and eyes-closed resting state data for user identification [60] [20] [44] [61] [27] [7] [13] [64], SVM was used in six studies, achieving a user identification accuracy range of 80% -

100% with only one study having an accuracy below 90%. Three studies use kNN, where a high CRR of 99.14% and accuracy of 99% was obtained. This would indicate that both SVM and kNN should be strongly considered for classifying resting state data. Other algorithms, such as LDA, QDA, and Cosine distance did not perform as strongly as SVM and kNN and are therefore considered less desirable for a resting state activity dataset. This survey can be expanded in the future by incorporating the analysis of additional state-of-the-art, which will enhance our spectrum of observation of the correlation between selection of authentication modules and performance.

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